

THE LEVEL OF READINES TRAINEE TEACHERS IN THE INSTITUTE OF TEACHER EDUCATION TECHNICAL EDUCATION CAMPUS FOR SPECIAL NEEDS STUDENTS IN TVET SUBJECTS

*¹Johnady Wong Tiong Hee, ²Mohd Ridzuan Padzil, ¹Hanani Harum Rasit, ³Alice WongMing Hiong, ⁴Christina Ting Yuer Ning, ⁵Esmond Yap Wei Yang

¹*Institut Pendidikan Guru Kampus Pendidikan Teknik, Negeri Sembilan, Malaysia*

*Jhsecretgalaxy9@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In Malaysia, studies on students with special needs in technical and vocational education are lacking. Therefore, this study aims to identify the level of readiness of trainee teachers towards the implementation of the teaching and learning process for technical and vocational subjects namely Design and Technology. This study uses a survey method using a 4-point Likert scale questionnaire as a research instrument involving a sample of 154 teacher trainees at the Technical Education Campus Teacher Education Institution who took the Design and Technology(RBT) course. The size of the selected respondents was by simple random sampling using Krejcie& Morgan's Sample Size Determination Table. Descriptive analysis was used to obtain the meanvalue, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage to see the level of preparedness of traineeteachers towards Special Needs Students (SNS) in TVET subjects. The findings of the study show the level of knowledge and skills of trainee teachers regarding the implementation of teaching and learning of Design and Technology subjects for students with Special Needs (SNS)which is overall at a moderate level. The results of the analysis found that the level of knowledgeand skills of trainee teachers at Teacher Education Institutions concerning the implementation ofthe teaching and learning of Design and Technology subjects for Students with Special Needs (SNS) needs to be improved. This study is expected to provide input on the level of preparednessof trainee teachers at the Technical Education Campus Teacher Education Institution in teachingstudents with special educational needs in TVET subjects. Improving the knowledge and skills ofDesign and Technology trainee teachers at the Technical Education Campus Teacher Education Institution will have a positive impact on the effectiveness of the teaching and learning delivered by the trainee teachers, which in turn can improve the quality of learning for Special Needs Students (SNS) in the classroom. In conclusion, every trainee teacher needs to be given sufficienttraining and education to help Special Needs Students (SNS) in Design and Technology subjects.

Keywords: Special Needs Students (SNS), Teaching and Learning Knowledge, Teaching and Learning Skills, Behavior Management, Technical and Vocational Education (TVET), RekaBentuk dan Teknologi (RBT)

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Students with Special Needs (SNS) have begun to gain attention and recognition worldwide. The Malaysian Ministry of Education (KPM) has designed and provided Technical and Vocational Education Training (TVET) for students with special needs (SNS) to allow them to acquire knowledge and skills training related to employment and self-management. As educators, teachers need to master the skills, especially the skills of educating, nurturing, and guiding students with special needs (SNS) so that they can develop and contribute to the nation's human resources. Therefore, teachers must be prepared and have extensive knowledge about SNS to manage the TVET program for SNS because this group needs a different way of education than ordinary students. Assessment of the level of readiness of trainee teachers for students with special needs in Design and Technology, also known as *Reka Bentuk dan Teknologi* (RBT), is essential to identify strengths and areas for improvement in the teacher preparation program. With that, this study aims to assess the level of readiness of trainee teachers who specialize in Design and Technology in teaching students with special needs for Design and Technology subjects. By assessing their readiness, we can gain insight into the effectiveness of current teacher training curricula in addressing the unique needs of students with special needs and identify areas for improvement. Not only that, the findings of this research will inform curriculum development, teaching strategies, and support mechanisms needed to equip teacher educators better to meet the needs of diverse SNS. This study was carried out to measure the level of readiness of trainee teachers in educating special needs students (SNS), including knowledge, skills, and student behaviour management.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In Malaysia, the Inclusive Education Program (IEP) has been created by the Ministry of Education Malaysia (MOE) at the pre-school, primary, secondary, and post-secondary levels as a basis for implementing the principle of "Education For All" (EFA). Undeniable, this Inclusive Education Program (IEP) allows potential special needs students (SNS) to follow academic and non-academic programs together with students in mainstream classes. That's because a teacher is considered very knowledgeable and experienced in the subjects they teach. However, the Inclusive Education Program (IEP) implemented in mainstream schools has become one of the challenges for non-special education teachers due to a lack of knowledge about special needs students from all aspects, such as cognitive, physical, emotional, and social. This statement is supported by the findings of Simmi, Rama, and Ishaan (2010), who state that mainstream classroom teachers are unprepared and feel afraid of the presence of special needs students (SNS). In addition, a previous Manimeegalai Govindasamy (2018) study also stated that most mainstream teachers are only qualified in certain core subjects. *Institut Pendidikan Guru Kampus Pendidikan Teknik* trainee teachers who specialize in Design and Technology are also ordinary mainstream teachers who lack the training and exposure to special education knowledge related to teaching techniques and methods to handle special needs students (SNS). This incident caused mainstream teachers to be less skilled in how to guide SNS.

Moreover, Design and Technology subjects have a higher risk of injury than other subjects because it involves using materials and tools to do practical work. Teachers who have never attended special education training to teach special needs students at school usually have insufficient professional knowledge and skills to teach effectively (Faiza Abbas, 2016). In this situation, it is clear that the student teachers bear the responsibility and the heavy pressure because they have to handle special needs students and regular students simultaneously during the teaching session for Design and Technology subjects.

Not only that, according to a study conducted by Pau Swee Lin & Mohd Hanafi Mohd Yasin (2021) regarding the level of knowledge and attitudes of mainstream teachers towards the Inclusive Education Program (IEP) in Sibul district. The study's findings also show that mainstream primary and secondary school teachers in the Sibul district have a moderate level of knowledge and a moderately high attitude towards IEP. Based on descriptive statistical analysis, the mean average result for the level of knowledge is 3.35, while the average mean score for the attitude items is 3.66. In addition, the findings of the study by Lee Kah Chian & Suziyani Mohamed (2021) show that preschool teachers' knowledge level in teaching SNS is at a moderately low level, where there is an average result of 2.65. According to the studies above, the differences in the results of these different studies are visible in different places and individuals have been shown.

Undeniable, based on the highlights of previous studies, it proves that mainstream teachers' preparedness level in terms of knowledge and skills in teaching SNS has not yet reached a high level. This refers to the study of Lee Keok Cheong & Sailajah Nair Sukumaran (2018); inclusive education often faces the problem of insufficient workforce training, lacks continuity, and is not adequately coordinated. Therefore, this study was conducted to see the overall level of readiness of *Institusi Pendidikan Guru Kampus Pendidikan Teknik* trainee teachers in teaching SNS for design and technology subjects.

METHODOLOGY

The research design used is a survey study. One of the aims of carrying out this review is to examine the level of willingness of *Institusi Pendidikan Guru Kampus Pendidikan Teknik* student teachers to carry out design and technology teaching for MBK so that action can be taken for improvement. This study uses a quantitative study design using research questions, namely Google Form, as a study instrument to be distributed to targeted respondents. Yee Sye Foong (2018) stated that the survey method efficiently collects large amounts of data at a low cost in a short period. This quantitative study was conducted on design and technology trainee teachers from *Institusi Pendidikan Guru Kampus Pendidikan Teknik* (IPGKPT). The data was analyzed using the descriptive analysis method to answer the research questions that were raised and then look at the level of preparedness of trainee teachers towards to examine the level of preparedness of trainee teachers towards students with special educational needs in the subject of Design and Technology (RBT).

The study population was a total of 260 trainee teachers from the Reka Bentuk dan Teknologi (RBT) course at the Technical Education Campus Teacher Education Institution. The study sample size involved in this study was 154 people based on Krejcie and Morgan's table (1970) using a simple random sampling method. This random sampling technique is the easiest and most suitable if the population has uniform or almost uniform characteristics (Fauzi, Jamal & Mohd Saifoul, 2014).

A questionnaire research instrument was used in this study to obtain data on the level of knowledge, skills, and readiness of trainee teachers towards the implementation of teaching and learning design and technology subjects for Special Needs Students (SNS). This research instrument was adapted and modified from Nurul Farahah and Suziyani's (2018) study regarding the readiness, knowledge, skills, and attitudes of special education teachers for learning disabilities to teach plant vocational skills. To strengthen the stability and capability of the questionnaire instrument used, language and content validity tests were conducted based on expert evaluations that fit the context of the study. The value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient obtained for the reliability test on 30 students is as much as $\alpha=0.892$. This value is acceptable and can be considered for the actual study (Hair, Babin, Money, and Samouel, 2003)

Descriptive analysis was used to obtain information on the research questions expressed through the percentage value, mean, and standard deviation using the software Statistic Package For Social Science (SPSS) version 26. To determine the level of readiness of trainee teachers, the division of the scale was divided into three levels, namely low, medium, and high based on Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Interpretation

Score Mean	Interpretation
1.00-2.33	Low
2.34-3.67	Moderate
3.68-5.00	High

Source: Nunnally & Bernstein (1994)

RESULTS AND FINDING

The findings of this survey are divided into four parts, which include the demographics of the respondents and the knowledge and skills of trainee teachers regarding the implementation of teaching and learning of design and technology subjects for Special Needs (SNS) students.

Respondent Demographic

Based on Table 3 below shows the background analysis of respondents in percentage and frequency based on the items in part A of the questionnaire.

Figure 1: Distribution of Respondent

Item	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	38	24.7%
Female	116	75.3%
Design and Technology Courses as		
Major	140	90.9%
Minor	14	9.1%

To study the level of readiness, the level of skill in the implementation of teaching and learning of Design and Technology subjects as well as the level of knowledge of student teachers in special needs student behaviour management, a total of 58 items were used in this questionnaire.

Research question 1:

Table 4 below shows the mean and standard deviation obtained for the 20 questions asked to the respondents to answer research question 1, which is "What is the level of knowledge of trainee teachers regarding the implementation of teaching and learning of Design and Technology subjects for Special Needs Students (SNS)?" "The results of the data analysis found that the overall average for this research question is at a moderate level, which is mean = 3.43, standard deviation = 0.41. The data obtained shows that question B9 recorded the highest mean of 3.77, while the lowest mean was recorded by question B11 at 2.89.

Table 4: Level of knowledge of trainee teachers regarding the implementation of teaching and learning of Design and Technology subjects for Special Needs Students (SNS)

No	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
B1.	The objective of TVET is to provide an opportunity for special needs students (SNS) with learning disabilities to acquire basic knowledge in design and technology.	3.56	0.547	Moderate
B2.	The concept of implementing design and technology for SNS is meaningful and enjoyable education.	3.76	0.429	High
B3.	Learning involves collaboration (cooperation with the school and external parties) in implementing design and technology teaching.	3.62	0.562	Moderate
B4.	Formative assessment aspects (assessment throughout the learning process and project outcomes) are present in design and technology.	3.66	0.527	Moderate
B5.	The implementation of design and technology teaching can produce special needs students who can live independently.	3.71	0.484	High
B6.	The implementation of design and technology teaching can produce special needs students with a positive mindset.	3.71	0.456	High
B7.	The implementation of design and technology teaching can produce disciplined special needs students.	3.62	0.514	Moderate
B8.	The implementation of design and technology teaching can produce special needs students with good character.	3.63	0.511	Moderate
B9.	The implementation of design and technology teaching can produce special needs, creative students.	3.77	0.420	High
B10.	The concept of information and communication technology (ICT) as an empowering tool in design and technology for special needs students.	3.68	0.508	High
B11.	I have sufficient knowledge in teaching special needs students at school in the subject of design and technology.	2.89	0.867	Moderate
B12.	I clearly understand each learning topic to deliver knowledge to special needs students at school.	3.12	0.787	Moderate
B13.	I have knowledge that can motivate students with special needs at school.	3.16	0.745	Moderate
B14.	I have knowledge that can motivate special needs students at school.	3.29	0.656	Moderate

B15.	I enjoy sharing knowledge with other teachers to identify special needs students at school.	3.33	0.696	Moderate
B16.	I have knowledge about self-management that is suitable for special needs students at school.	3.06	0.756	Moderate
B17.	I have ICT knowledge to be applied in design and technology teaching and learning sessions for special needs students at school.	3.25	0.689	Moderate
B18.	I know how to use appropriate teaching aids (TAs) for the learning of special needs students at school.	3.11	0.737	Moderate
B19.	I know about producing teaching aids (TAs) for the learning of special needs students at school.	3.11	0.763	Moderate
B20.	Teaching aids (TAs) as empowering tools in design and technology for special needs students.	3.56	0.560	Moderate
Average		3.43	0.410	Moderate

Table 5 below shows a total of 17 questions submitted to study research question 2, which is "What is the level of skill of trainee teachers in the implementation of teaching and learning of design and technology subjects for Special Needs Students (SNS)?" ". Based on the data analysis, the overall mean is at 3.04 with a standard deviation of 0.544, which is also at a moderate level. The highest mean was recorded by question B36, 3.29, while the lowest was by question B21, which was 2.84.

Table 5: Mean skill level of trainee teachers regarding the implementation of teaching and learning design and technology subjects for Special Needs Students (SNS)

No	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
B21.	I am skilled at creating examination questions for design and technology subjects that are suitable for the abilities of special needs students.	2.84	0.745	Moderate
B22.	I am skilled in distinguishing between primary, unit, and content questions in design and technology examinations.	2.88	0.770	Moderate
B23.	I am skilled in implementing individual learning plans (ILPs) for design and technology subjects for special needs students.	2.86	0.745	Moderate
B24.	I am skilled in integrating various teaching strategies for design and technology.	3.18	0.687	Moderate
B25.	I am skilled in designing design and technology projects according to the modules I have built accurately.	3.08	0.723	Moderate
B26.	I am skilled in creating a schedule for implementing design and technology projects based on the suitability of the achievement level of special needs students.	2.97	0.745	Moderate
B27.	I can complete various activities planned in design and technology within the designated time frame.	3.08	0.682	Moderate
B28.	I am skilled in ensuring that students with learning disabilities actively participate in design and technology.	2.98	0.736	Moderate
B29.	I am skilled in ensuring that special needs			

	students complete learning exercises within the designated time frame.	3.10	0.712	Moderate
B30.	I am proficient in identifying the challenges faced by special needs students throughout the process of design and technology teaching.	3.03	0.656	Moderate
B31.	I am skilled in assessing the work produced by special needs students throughout the process of design and technology teaching.	3.07	0.706	Moderate
B32.	I am skilled in preparing scoring instruments that outline specific criteria and standards to assess the work or achievements of special needs students.	2.93	0.733	Moderate
B33.	I am skilled in integrating the Internet into design and technology's teaching and learning process for special needs students.	3.24	0.627	Moderate
B34.	I am skilled in effectively delivering ideas in teaching design and technology to special needs students.	3.21	0.623	Moderate
B35.	I am skilled in disciplining special needs students through teaching design and technology.	3.05	0.684	Moderate
B36.	I am skilled in collaborating with colleagues to plan design and technology activities for special needs students.	3.29	0.547	Moderate
B37.	I am skilled in communicating with special needs students.	2.96	0.749	Moderate
	Average	3.04	0.544	Moderate

Research question 3:

Table 6 below answers research question 3: "What is the level of knowledge of trainee teachers in the management of the behavior of Special Needs Students during the implementation of the teaching and learning of design and technology subjects?" which consists of 21 questions. Data analysis obtained the average result mean = 3.53 and standard deviation = 0.461, which is also at a moderate level. Data analysis shows that the highest mean value is 3.69 on question B51 and the lowest on question B55 is 3.36.

Table 6: Level of knowledge of trainee teachers in the management of the behaviour of Special Needs Students during the implementation of teaching and learning of design and technology subjects

No	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
B38.	Distinguishing between positive behavior and negative behavior.	3.59	0.506	Moderate
B39.	Understanding the importance of behavior management for special needs students.	3.61	0.515	Moderate
B40.	Understanding the components of behavior management for special needs students so that they can practice positive behavior and adapt well to community life.	3.49	0.629	Moderate

B41. Understanding the components of behavior management for special needs students so they can manage their emotions and adapt well to community life.	3.43	0.635	Moderate
B42. Understanding the components of behavior management for special needs students so that students can build self-confidence and adapt well to community life.	3.45	0.627	Moderate
B43. Understanding behavior management is one of the components in the field of life management for special needs students.	3.49	0.608	Moderate
B44. Understanding the goals and objectives of behavior management for special needs students.	3.45	0.605	Moderate
B45. Understanding the impact of behavior management on the teaching and learning process in the classroom.	3.51	0.574	Moderate
B46. Understanding the types of problematic behaviors.	3.55	0.537	Moderate
B47. Understand the meaning of behavior management.	3.62	0.514	Moderate
B48. Understand the steps to shape positive behavior in special needs students.	3.44	0.667	Moderate
B49. Understanding that positive reinforcement can enhance targeted behavior.	3.55	0.561	Moderate
B50. Understanding that social reinforcement such as praise and smiles can encourage positive behavior.	3.61	0.515	Moderate
B51. Understanding that rewards can provide motivation.	3.69	0.479	High
B52. Understanding that rewards can encourage positive behavior.	3.65	0.518	Moderate
B53. Understanding that rewards can be given in the form of points or stickers and diversified.	3.59	0.556	Moderate
B54. Understanding that positive reinforcement can reduce negative behavior.	3.63	0.511	Moderate
B55. Understanding that the technique of Time-Out Modification involves removing a student from the learning group for a specified time.	3.36	0.655	Moderate
B56. Understanding that punishment can reduce negative behavior.	3.41	0.710	Moderate
B57. Understanding that warning can reduce negative behavior.	3.49	0.618	Moderate
B58. Understanding that negative reinforcement can increase positive behavior.	3.45	0.647	Moderate
Average	3.527	0.461	Moderate

DISCUSSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The overall data analysis of this study shows that the level of teacher trainee readiness is at a moderate level in terms of knowledge and skills. This finding shows that trainee teachers are not yet fully aware of the implementation of the teaching and learning process for design and technology subjects for students with special needs (SNS). The results of this finding are in line with the findings of a study by Pau Swee Lin & Mohd Hanafi Mohd Yasin (2021), who also found that the level of mainstream teachers' knowledge of special education is still at a moderate level. According to the findings of the data, there is no denying the level of knowledge and skills of trainee teachers concerning the teaching and learning process of design and technology subjects for SNS still needs to be improved. This lack of knowledge and skills will cause the teaching and learning process to not be implemented effectively and achieve the learning objectives that have been set. This is because students with special needs require a lot of attention and training. In addition, the teacher's skill level is a domain that affects the effectiveness and implementation of a teaching and learning method in the classroom (Hover, Hicks & Dack, 2016). The findings of the study provide important information that trainee teachers still need more specific training and guidance before they can teach students with special needs for RBT subjects in schools in the future.

The findings of this study hope to bring awareness to the Ministry of Education Malaysia (MOE) that prospective design and technology trainee teachers under the teacher education institute are still not prepared about how to implement teaching and learning for design and technology subjects to SNS. This issue is mainly seen in question B11, which has the lowest mean score of all study items. It shows that most teachers admit they lack sufficient knowledge to teach special needs at school for design and technology subjects. Through the results of this study, it is hoped that the MOE can provide workshops, courses, or special training programs related to implementing design and technology teaching for SNS. For example, the PLC Program (Professional Learning Community) involves special education teachers trained in teaching SNS to provide more helpful input. Trained teachers can provide ideas, understanding, teaching approaches, and suitable techniques for SNS in design and technology. Trained teachers can help student teachers identify SNS needs and plan appropriate lessons. According to Zagona et al. (2017), found that there was a significant difference in knowledge about inclusive education between mainstream teachers and special education teachers. Special education teachers are said to have more knowledge related to inclusive education because they have a foundation related to inclusiveness that has been studied at university.

Conclusions

In conclusion, it was found that the level of readiness for students with special educational needs in the subjects of Design and Technology (RBT) is at a moderate level. This finding shows that although trainee teachers have specific knowledge and skills in implementing design and technology teaching and learning, there is still a lack of knowledge and skills in managing the teaching and learning process, especially for students with special educational needs. Therefore, a more organized involvement of various parties such as the Ministry of Education, IPGM, Teacher Education Division, and JPN, is necessary to design and provide training and education that focuses on the education and management of students with special needs in the field of TVET. If this step is implemented perfectly, likely, the abilities and achievements of students with special needs in design and technology subjects will be better and help increase their potential in addition to providing equal opportunities in education.

REFERENCE

- Abbas, F., Zafar, A., & Naz, T. (2016). Footstep towards Inclusive Education. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(10), 48-52.
- Cheong, L. K., & Sukumaran, S. N. (2018). Pendidikan Inklusif. *Shah Alam: Oxford Fajar Sdn. Bhd.*
- Chian, L. K., & Mohamed, S. (2021). Tahap Pengetahuan Guru dalam Pelaksanaan Pendidikan Inklusif di Kelas Prasekolah. *Jurnal Dunia Pendidikan*, 3(2), 253-260.
- Fauzi Hussin, Jamal Ali, & Mohd Saifoul Zamzuri Noor. (2014). *Kaedah penyelidikan & analisis data SPSS*. Sintok: Penerbit Universiti Utara Malaysia.
- Govindasamy, M. (2018). Persepsi Terhadap Program Pendidikan Inklusif (PPI) Oleh Guru Aliran Perdana Dan Guru Pendidikan Khas Di Daerah Seberang Perai Tengah. *Jurnal Paradigma*, 17, 172-89.
- Hover, S.V., Hicks, D., & Dack, H. (2016). From Source to Evidence? Teachers' Use of Historical Sources in Their Classrooms. *The Social Studies*, 107(6), 209-217.
- J. Hair, B. Babin, A. Money and P. Samouel, "Essentials of Business Research Methods," Lehigh Publishing, 2003
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(3), 607-610.
- Nunnally, J. C., & Bernstein. 1994. *Psychometric Theory* (3rd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill Nurul Farahah Derapa, Suziyani Mohamed. (2018). Kesiediaan Guru Pendidikan Khas dalam Melaksanakan Mata Pelajaran. *Jurnal Ortopedagogia, Volume 4 Nomor 1 Juli: 66-71 Kesiediaan Guru Pendidikan Khas dalam Melaksanakan Mata Pelajaran Asas Tanaman*.
- Swee Li, Pau, Mohd Yasin, Mohd Hanafi. (2021). Pengetahuan Dan Sikap Guru Aliran Perdana Terhadap Program Pendidikan Inklusif Di Daerah Sib. *Jurnal Dunia Pendidikan*, [S.l.], v. 3, n. 1, p. 515-529,
- Simmi Chhabra, Rama Srivastava & Ishaan Srivastava. (2010). Inclusive education in Botswana: The perceptions of school teachers. *Journal of Disability Policy Studies*, 20(4), 219-228.
- Sye Foong Yee. (2018). *A Phenomenological Inquiry into Science Teachers' Case Method Learning*. Springer Nature Singapore.
- Zagona A. L., Kurth J. A., MacFarland S. Z. C. (2017). Teachers' views of their preparation for inclusive education and collaboration. *Teacher Education and Special Education*, 40, 163-178.